

Questioning the choice overload effect through design research

Maria Valéria Assis^{1,2}
maria.assis@aalto.fi

Leandro Tonetto¹
ltonetto@unisinis.br

¹Universidade do Vale do Rio dos Sinos, Brazil

²Aalto University, Finland

Abstract Choice overload is a negative effect caused by a great variety of options in the user's choice experience. Researches have shown that, with the increase in the number of options, pleasure and satisfaction were negatively affected. Our aim was to measure the impact of the diversity of alternatives in the beauty and hygiene segment over the user choice experience. In an experiment (n=96), the diverse quantity of choice was manipulated using different types of packaging, a characteristic element of design projects. Based on sales catalog's information from a major company in this segment, three experimental conditions were generated: the first had 50% of the average amount of products found on the catalogs; the second had the average number of options found for the products; the third encompassed 50% more from the mean options from the catalogs. Results indicated the opposite of other researches on choice overload: users had more positive experiences when facing the biggest quantity of options (50% above the average of the quantity found in the market). These results have implications to product portfolio planning and can be used as a base to provide pleasurable experiences to consumers.

Keywords Choice overload, Choice experience, Amount of alternatives

Introduction

In the contemporary world, designers tries to deal with technical aspects of projects, as well as its impact on user experiences. It is a common assumption in the modern society that the bigger the number of choices, the better. People are accustomed to have different options to choose from and many express a desire for having more options. That is not necessarily a good idea, as there are cognitive limits to how much information people can process about products and services when making decisions. Following this reasoning, the choosing task often is felt as suffering (Iyengar; Agrawal, 2010).

According to Iyengar and Agrawal (2010), psychological studies have consistently shown the difficulty of comparing and contrasting attributes of more than seven different elements. In addition, people tend to become overloaded and frustrated when confronted with cognitive requirements of choice. The authors state that, as a result, people may (1) abdicate to make a choice completely, (2) reach to a more familiar choice, or even (3) make a poor decision, leading to a lower satisfaction.

While people may often be attracted by the variety of options in the market, it has been suggested that this overabundance can lead to adverse consequences, such as: decreased motivation to make the choice, to commit to a choice, or to make any choice (Iyengar; Lepper, 2000); a decrease in the strength of preference and satisfaction with the chosen option (Chernev, 2003; Iyengar; Lepper, 2000), and an increase in negative emotions, including disappointment and

regret (Schwartz, 2004).

This phenomenon has been called "choice overload" (Iyengar; Lepper, 2000); the "problem of too much choice"; the "tyranny of choice" (Schwartz, 2004); or the "too-much-choice-effect" (Scheibehenne; Greifeneder; Todd, 2009). The consensus among these terms is the idea of the adverse consequences caused by the increased number of options to choose from, which can negatively impact the user choice experience. Commonly viewed as a marketing thread, handling choice overload becomes a design problem as the area seeks development on understanding all the factors involved in managing design and, hence, the management of the product portfolio diversity.

Therefore, this study intends to understand the aspects which influence the occurrence of choice overload. Using a basic design element, the packaging and its shape, which was chosen for the easy manipulation by isolating one variable without being affected by others. This research aims to collaborate to avoid choice overload, in order to promote a positive choice experience for users facing a diversity of options. In this study, a positive choice experience is defined as the one where the user feels pleasure, manage to choose without difficulty, is less frustrated and more satisfied with the choice experience (Iyengar & Lepper, 2000; Shah & Wolford, 2007; Kobayashi et al., 2011).

Choice overload

Researchers on the phenomenon of choice overload, according to Scheibehenne, Greifeneder and Todd

(2010), argue that the negative effects do not always occur, but depend on certain prerequisites. An important precondition is the lack of familiarity or previous preference among the options so that the choice maker do not choose only something that matches their own preferences (Iyengar; Lepper, 2000). Chernev (2003) showed that people with clear previous preferences prefer to choose from larger assortments. For these people, the probability of choice and satisfaction increased with the number of options to choose from, the opposite of choice overload. For this reason, experiments with choice overload use unfamiliar options to whom will make the choice, thus avoiding strong previous preference for a particular option and, consequently, a highly selective search process that allow participants to ignore most part of the assortment (Scheibehenne; Greifeneder; Todd, 2009).

According to Shah and Wolford (2007), most research in this topic compared only two size groups, with number options with an average of 6 units (small group) and 24 (major group). Although the number of choice options is the core hypothesis on choice overload, there is no exact definition of what constitutes a lot of options.

A variable to consider is the perceived variety of the assortment, since the perception of variety can be equal to the real variety or not (Kahn, 1998). The author believes that large assortments can be negatively perceived by consumers if, instead of offering choice possibilities, they seem monumental and frustrating. As an example, the author mentions a Chinese restaurant menu on which the selection usually involves four types of meat (chicken, shrimp, beef and pork) and different sauces. Every possible type of combination is listed separately, making the perceived range to be large, while the actual assortment would be better understood if it was described in only two attributes. Thus, the author believes that when the array is processed in a simple and enjoyable way or when the consumer is motivated, the perception of a lot of variety is better than a little variety. However, when the processing is difficult, little variety might be preferred.

There are two factors which contribute to the perceived variety, according to Kahn (1998): the number of acceptable choices and the desired amount of diversity among the items. For the author, the sheer number of options is a type of diversity. For example, an ice cream parlor offering 31 flavors appears to offer more flexibility and range than the one that offers two or three options, regardless of which flavors. According to the author, if the user sees little or no difference between items of a product class, then the perception of abundance will also be low. Thus, the amount of diversity that consumers desire in an assortment is a function of the acceptability of the items and the distinction among these.

For Scheibehenne, Greineder and Todd (2010), on a theoretical perspective, the choice overload hypothesis defies most models of choice in psychology and economics, which believe that the increase of a set of

options does not leave the decision maker in a worse situation. In a practical perspective, a decrease on satisfaction or motivation due to the diversity of choice would require companies to rethink their practices of providing more and more kinds of products because they could increase their success if they had less to offer.

To Iyengar and Agrawal (2010) most companies do not reduce the number of products they offer because they are afraid of losing shelf space to competitors. However, the authors suggest that a careful cut can reduce costs, increase sales and improve the experience of choice for consumers. Kahn (1998) believes that, often, large assortments contain many redundant or duplicate options, which makes the choice more difficult. According to the author, to reduce users' confusion and maintain a sense of variety, extinguishing redundant items is enough.

In the mid-1990s, when Procter & Gamble (multinational of the health and beauty segment) decreased the range of the anti-dandruff shampoo Head & Shoulders, from 26 to 15, by eliminating less popular ones: sales increased by 10% (Goldstein, 2001 apud Shah; Wolford, 2007). This strategy, according to Kahn (1998), increased profitability and, in some categories, consumers perceived the assortment better with 35% less amount of units.

Thus, Iyengar and Agrawal (2010) propose that, if the market for a product is saturated with a variety of options, one should not seek a competitive advantage by providing more choices on the shelves. Instead, the authors suggest turning the selection process in a more positive and easier experience for consumers.

Hypothesis

As a stimulus to support this research, we selected the hygiene and beauty sector. According to the Brazilian Association of the Cosmetic, Toiletry and Perfumery Industry (ABIHPEC), Brazil is the third largest consumer in the world of cosmetics. Hygiene and beauty products are distributed in Brazil mainly in three ways: direct sales, network of franchised stores and traditional channels (supermarkets and pharmacies, etc.).

Based on this data, it was developed and experiment in order to measure the choice overload effect. The premise of this study, and of studies on choice overload (Iyengar and Lepper, 2000; Shah and Wolford, 2007; Kobayashi, Miki, Hiroyasu et al, 2011) is that, while providing many choices initially seem attractive to the participant, it can impair various aspects of the quality of choice experience. We then formulated the following hypothesis:

H₁: with the reduced number of choice alternatives, the user has more pleasure in the experience;

H₂: with fewer options, the user has less difficulty on making the choice;

H₃: with fewer options, the user feels less frustration with the choice experience;

H₄: with limited number of choice alternatives, the user has greater satisfaction in the experience.

On the perception of the amount of options to choose from, the hypothesis is that:

H₅: the user perceives he/she has many choices (too many alternatives) when finding a set with greater diversity of options than usually found in the market.

Scheibehenne et al. (2009) proposed that users with well-defined preferences before making the choice prefer more choice alternatives, as they have more chance of having their own to match. The authors suggest that the lack of clear goals and preferences before a decision can moderate the effect of choice overload, as individuals with well-defined preferences are more willing to make a choice and be satisfied with the alternative chosen among many options, since their preference can be matched. In addition, the likelihood of these preferences are met increases with the number of options available, leading to the opposite effect to the decision makers, where more is better. Therefore:

H₆: users with prior preferences among the evaluated products enjoy large amounts of alternatives.

The hypothesis will be tested using the data obtained in the experiment described below.

Methods

The experiment examined the effect of the number of options (independent variable) - manipulated through the diversity of shapes of hygiene and beauty products packaging – on pleasure, difficulty, frustration, satisfaction and perception of quantity, on the consumer's choice experience (dependent variables). The packages were chosen as a visual stimulation, as they allow easy manipulation of the shape variable without other interferences such as color, brand and texture.

The quantities of options used in the experiment were important for the research design. As identified through the analysis of empirical studies described in the introduction, it is not clear how the amount used in other experiments has been set. In their studies, Iyengar and Lepper (2000, p. 996) defined a limited amount of choice in about six units "as presented in previous experiments", and the extensive choice condition with number of options "reasonably large, but not ecologically unusual". Thus, it was detected the need to establish a parameter to relate what is a small, a medium or a large amount of packaging.

In this study, the amount of choice in the catalogs was defined from a mean of shampoo, conditioner and liquid soap options present in the Natura brand catalogs. This company is appointed as leader on the direct selling market in Brazil (COMESTICOSBR, 2010), distributing 24 books/magazines in cycles throughout the year. These catalogs are printed or can be accessed through the company website.

For the sample, it was used magazines from the cycles 11/2011 to 9/2012 (totaling 15 cycles), present in the Natura website in the period of 8th to 15th of May, 2012. This time frame was set to stipulate a universe of which the data would be acquired, ensuring the neutrality of the research. The magazines of this period were fully examined in order to count the amount of packaging of shampoo, conditioner and liquid soap presented. For the counting of products, two criteria were determined: it was only considered products which contained the words "shampoo", "conditioner" and "liquid soap" in their name; refill packs composing a set were not counted. This resulted in the averages: 21.47 (SD = 1.37) shampoos, 20.24 (SD = 1.64) conditioners and 14.71 (SD = 2.37) liquid soaps.

To manipulate the variables in the experiment, it was determined an average of the total number of shampoo, conditioner and liquid soap containers presented in the catalogs. From this average three groups were defined, two experimental groups (EG) and one control group (CG): (1) 50% of the average amount of options (reduced condition, experimental group 1 - EG1), (2) the average amount of options detected in the evaluated catalogs (market average, control group – CG) and (3) 150% of the average amount in the catalogs (expanded condition, experimental group 2 - EG2), as can be seen in Table 1. Therefore, the variable 'amount of alternatives' was manipulated in three levels.

The means were rounded to simplify the calculation and provide integers for the amount of packaging used in the catalog simulation on the experiment.

Instrument and procedures for data collection

The data collection procedure was carried out at universities computer rooms. Teachers were contacted, with authorization from the universities administration, and the students were taken to the laboratory, together with the researchers.

Three catalogs were produced in Adobe Indesign software for different manipulation conditions (reduced condition (EG1), market average (CG) and expanded condition, EG2). For the catalogs, it was selected images from an image bank from the internet,

Table 1. Average of packages per group.

Group	Shampoo	Conditioner	Liquid soap
50% (EG1: reduced condition)	11 (10,5)	10	7
100% (CG: market average)	21	20	14
150% (EG2: expanded condition)	32 (31,5)	30	21

Source: The authors.

and these were treated in Adobe Photoshop to have the same color (Figure 1).

In the rapport participants were asked to imagine they needed to buy the products - shampoo, conditioner, liquid soap - to their homes and they should choose one of each product from the catalog. Also, the questionnaire was answered individually. The data collection took in average 20 minutes and was conducted between August and October of 2012 in higher education institutions in Southern Brazil.

The catalog was available on a website to be accessed by the participants. On the website, the instructions for the participant were to initially browse the catalogue until the end and then complete the questionnaire. Everyone who accessed the website saw only one of the three catalogs. Participants did not know about the differences of catalogs, and the experimenter did not know which catalog the participants would see, since the process was totally random.

After reading the instructions and browse the entire catalog, participants filled out a questionnaire divided into: record of the choices and participant information, experience of choice evaluation, and perception about the number of options to choose from. In the first part, participants recorded their choices, indicating the page on which the product was found, allowing the simulation of a real choice made with the catalog. Also, participants completed questions about gender, age and occupation. The second stage of the questionnaire was based on Iyengar and Lepper (2000), in order to evaluate the user choice experience. Responses were supplied through a Likert scale from one (1 - not at all) to seven (7 - extremely). Thus, the questionnaire sought to examine how the choice experience was pleasurable ("How much did you enjoy making the choice?"), difficult ("Did you find it difficult to make the choice?"), satisfactory ("How happy did you feel making the choice?") and frustrating ("How frustrated you felt when you made the choice?").

Besides the choice experience, in the third stage, the questionnaire included questions to assess the users' perceptions about the number of options provided. It was asked participants if they thought they had the right number of options for shampoo, conditioner and liquid soap packaging, in order to make the choice. ("Do you think you had the right number of shampoo options in order to make the choice?"; "Do you think you had the right number of conditioner options in order to make the choice?"; "Do you think you had the right number of liquid soap options in order to make the choice?"). The answers were given on a Likert scale of seven points, anchored in three points: one (1) equivalent to "I felt I had very few options to make the choice, four (4) "I had the right number of options to make the choice" and seven (7) to "No, I had too many options to make the choice".

Another question served to assess whether the participant's preferences influenced the response, according to the prior preference hypothesis

Figure 1. Catalogue example for the reduced condition (EG1).

(Scheibehenne et al., 2009). This item was evaluated by the question "If you buy any of these products, how much would you say the choices you normally do influenced the choices in this research?". Answers ranged from "extremely influenced", "influenced a lot", "moderately influenced", "somewhat influenced" to "not influenced at all".

At this stage, a final question was added to ensure the users have flipped through the entire catalog before answering the questionnaire: "Have you looked at all the products before making the choice?" with the answers "yes" or "no". The respondents that chose "no" were excluded from the research.

Sample and sampling

Ninety-six (96) undergraduate students participated on the experiment (47.9% were female and 52.1% male), of which 32 were exposed to the reduced condition (EG1), 31 to the market average (CG) and 31 to the expanded condition (EG2).

Instruments and procedures for data analysis

Responses were electronically recorded through spreadsheets in Google Docs and converted to SPSS format. Descriptive statistics were held regarding the identification variables (gender, age) and Analysis of Variance (ANOVAS) between the answers given to questions relating to the dependent variables by the three different groups. Post-hoc enabled the comparison among the three groups. Pearson correlations were made between the perception of having the right number of options to make the choice and the prior preference for a product variable.

Results

The results obtained by manipulating the amount of product choices can be seen in Table 2.

No significant differences were detected between the means of agreement on issues about pleasure with the choice ($F(2, 93) = 0.144, p > 0.05$); difficulty ($F(2, 93) = 1.258, p > 0.05$); satisfaction ($F(2, 93) = 0.599, p > 0.05$); and frustration ($F(2, 93) = 0.475, p > 0.05$).

It was detected, on the question about the perception of having the right number of shampoo options in order to make a choice, that there is an effect on the

amount of alternatives on the assessment of having the right number of options to make the choice ($F(2, 93) = 5.41, p < 0.05$). Comparative analyzes between groups (Post Hoc) showed that the mean agreement of the expanded condition group (EG2), in relation to having the right number of options to choose from, can be considered greater than the reduced condition group (EG1) ($p < 0.05$) Cohen's effect suggests a large ($d=0.83$) significance. Furthermore, the mean agreement of the expanded condition group (EG2) can be considered greater than the mean of the control group (CG) ($p < 0.10$). Cohen's effect size value suggests a small to medium significance ($d=0,28$).

On the question about the perception of having the right number of choices of conditioner to choose from, it was detected the effect of the number of alternatives on the assessment of having the right number of options ($F(2, 93) = 5.93, p < 0.05$). In the comparative analysis between the groups (Post Hoc), the average agreement level of the expanded condition group (EG2) ($p < 0.05$), compared to having the right number of options to choose from, can be considered higher than the mean of the reduced condition group (EG1). For this comparison, Cohens effect size value is high

($d=0,76$). Also, the mean agreement of expanded condition group (EG2) can be considered greater than the mean of the control group (CG) ($p < 0.05$), with a small ($d=0,06$) Cohen's effect size significance.

About the number of liquid soap options, it was also detected the effect of the amount of alternatives on the evaluation of having the right number of options to select from ($F(2, 93) = 8.38, p < 0.001$). Comparative analyzes between groups (Post Hoc) showed that the average agreement of the expanded condition group (EG2) ($p < 0.05$), compared to having the right number of options to choose from, can be considered greater than the mean of the reduced condition group (EG1). Cohen's effect suggests a large ($d=0,98$) significance. Also, the mean agreement level of the control group (CG) can be considered greater than the mean of the reduced condition group (EG1) ($p < 0.05$) – with a high ($d=0,82$) Cohen's effect significance – and less than the mean of the expanded condition group (EG2) ($p < 0.05$), which shows a small ($d=0,19$) Cohen's effect value.

Despite detecting several significant effects, the choice overload effect was not found, since the diversity of alternatives did not generate adverse consequences to

Table 2. Experiment's descriptive results.

Questions	Experimental group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
How much did you enjoy making the choice?	50% (EG1: reduced condition)	32	4,31	1,60
	100% (CG: Market mean)	33	4,27	1,31
	150% (EG2: expanded condition)	31	4,13	1,36
	Total	96	4,24	1,41
Did you find it difficult making the choice?	50% (EG1: reduced condition)	32	3,44	2,00
	100% (CG: Market mean)	33	3,33	1,81
	150% (EG2: expanded condition)	31	4,06	2,13
	Total	96	3,60	1,99
How satisfied were you about making the choice?	50% (EG1: reduced condition)	32	4,91	1,77
	100% (CG: Market mean)	33	4,48	1,62
	150% (EG2: expanded condition)	31	4,61	1,33
	Total	96	4,67	1,58
How frustrated were you about making the choice?	50% (EG1: reduced condition)	32	2,41	1,62
	100% (CG: Market mean)	33	2,58	1,90
	150% (EG2: expanded condition)	31	2,84	1,77
	Total	96	2,60	1,76
Did you feel you had the right number of shampoo options to make the choice?	50% (EG1: reduced condition)	32	4,22	1,58
	100% (CG: Market mean)	33	5,09	1,70
	150% (EG2: expanded condition)	31	5,55	1,61
	Total	96	4,95	1,71
Did you feel you had the right number of conditioner options to make the choice?	50% (EG1: reduced condition)	32	4,13	1,48
	100% (CG: Market mean)	33	5,22	1,54
	150% (EG2: expanded condition)	31	5,32	1,64
	Total	96	4,90	1,63
Did you feel you had the right number of liquid soap options to make the choice?	50% (EG1: reduced condition)	32	3,56	1,56
	100% (CG: Market mean)	33	4,91	1,74
	150% (EG2: expanded condition)	31	5,26	1,91
	Total	96	4,57	1,87

Source: The authors.

the choice experience. The opposite has been identified: users perceive to have the right number of options to choose among different forms of shampoo, conditioner and liquid soap.

Furthermore, it was executed a Pearson correlation analysis between the issues related to the perception of having the right number of options to choose from (one for each product) and the perception of having suffered influence of previous preferences about the choices made (also assessed using specific questions for each product evaluated). The analysis considered the sample divided by groups (control group and experimental groups), which showed only a correlation (negative) significant referred to the choice of the conditioner in the control condition ($r = -0.464$, $p < 0.01$). Thus, it was not observed consistent correlations between the variables prior preferences in the segment and the perception of suitability of product mix increased, so that they do not relate.

Discussion and conclusion

The number of options to choose in the experiments were set from the average of the total number of packaging of shampoo, conditioner and liquid soap found in the Natura catalogs (cycles from 11/2011 to 9/2012). This time frame was set to determine an universe where the data would be acquired and guarantee the neutrality of the research. It also differentiates this research from others reviewed (Iyengar, Lepper, 2000; Scheibehenne, Greifeneder, Todd, 2009; Kobayashi, Miki, Hiroyasu et al, 2011; Shah, Wolford, 2007), because it was established a parameter to decide the amount of alternatives. From the average amount of the total number of packaging found, three groups were established: the market average condition (100%), other with the reduced number (50%) and a third condition with an expanded number of options (150%). Thus, it was possible to establish what is a small, a medium or a large amount of packaging, in relation to the market average.

The variables analyzed in the experiment, based on Iyengar and Lepper (2000), involved pleasure, difficulty of choosing, frustration, satisfaction and perception of right number of options in relation to the choice experience. The hypothesis H_1 to H_5 were denied: the results show that users perceive as more appropriate the set with expanded options.

Choice overload, pointed out by different authors (Iyengar, Lepper, 2000; Schwartz, 2000; Scheibehenne, Greifeneder, Todd, 2009) as an effect that causes adverse issues to the choice experience across diversity of alternatives, was not found in this study. Thus, it is noteworthy to designers that one can work with extensive product lines and still provide positive experiences to the user. Choosing through catalogs, according to the experiment results, appears distinct from other forms of decision discussed in the introduction of this paper. Portfolio management of the product in the segment deserves to be designed differently: more can be better.

This result is in favor of the arguments mentioned by Scheibehenne, Greifeneder and Todd (2009), who

question the hypothesis of choice overload. According to the authors, large assortments may have advantages, including: a wide variety of choices increases the probability of satisfying different individuals and thus serves to individuality and plurality; a wide variety available in one location reduces the cost of looking for more options; allow for direct comparisons among options, making it easy to have a global idea of the distribution quality. All these factors lead to a better informed and more confident choice. Hence, future studies on choice overload could consider the variety moderator in the beauty and hygiene segment.

A significant correlation between the perception of having the right number of options to choose from, and the previous preference variable was found on one (conditioner) of the three products used. The result contradicts what Scheibehenne, Greifeneder and Todd (2009) stated about the possible too-much-choice effect moderator. According to the authors, as the number of options increases, the more likely a consumer with well-defined preferences will find what pleases him/herself among the options. Therefore, the H_6 hypothesis, which proposed that users with prior preference appreciate lots of alternatives, was denied. This does not mean that they appreciate or not large sets of products to make the choice, but it means that the variables preference and suitability assessment of the set of alternatives were not related consistently in the study.

Also, the number of attributes to be evaluated by the consumer when making a choice may be taken into consideration. In this research, simple elements were employed: the shape of hygiene and beauty products. That's possibly the reason why participants preferred the expanded number of options, because there were not many attributes, besides the shape, to evaluate in order to make the choice. In the experiments analyzed, except for Kobayashi, Miki, Hiroyasu et al. (2011), the chosen products had more than one attribute, such as the pens used by Shah and Wolford (2007) or the list of restaurants and charities offered by Scheibehenne, Greifeneder and Todd (2010). Therefore, future studies could consider a wider range of attributes in the investigated segment.

Scheibehenne, Greifeneder and Todd (2010) point out the choice environment issue, about how researches on choice overload commonly refer to satisfaction with the chosen option, instead of the choice experience as a whole. In this research, the choice experience was evaluated in an artificial environment. Therefore, the research context may have caused the non detection of choice overload, since the decision did not offer consequences of a real choice, in the long term. Another future research opportunity is indicated by pursuing studies in more natural settings.

The experiment results show how important the perception of the number of options by the user is. Kahn (1998) believes that this variable must be considered when working with large amounts of products – preferred by the participants on this research - for the consumer to positively experience

the choice possibilities. The author indicates that it is important to know the user preferences, present a number that present flexibility of options, and items distinct from each other.

Therefore, by providing an extensive product portfolio in the hygiene and beauty sector, it is important to consider the perceived range variable, indicated by Kahn (1998). According to the author, the range should contain different items, so that the consumer perceives a varied and flexible assortment. Otherwise, with very similar items to each other, the user can negatively perceive the amount of items, causing frustration when making a choice.

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